

BEST PRACTICE

This is part of a series of guidance documents produced by the NADIR FP7 project. There are various international and national standards in place for undertaking infectious work in animals with pathogens that require high containment facilities. These guidance documents be examples of how these can be practically interpreted

Best Practice for Fumigation using Formaldehyde (Microbiological Safety Cabinets, Isolators and Rooms)

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INTRODUCTION

1.1 Scope of this Document

- 1.1.1 Fumigation is defined as an operation in which a substance is released into the atmosphere so as to form a gas to control or kill pests or other undesirable organisms. This document only applies to formaldehyde fumigation but a lot of the basic principles could be applied to other fumigants such as hydrogen peroxide vapours treatment.
- 1.1.2 There are legal and moral responsibilities on organisations to ensure that staff remains safe while at work. All activities involving formaldehyde and other fumigants must be assessed to ensure that the risks are controlled where necessary
- 1.1.3 . This document aims to:
- Define the requirements for formaldehyde fumigation;
 - Outline the validation requirements to demonstrate successful fumigation;
 - Define the training requirements; and
 - Outline the documentation and record keeping required.

TRAINING

- 2.1 Fumigation must only be performed by trained and competent staff.

- 2.2 Training must include:
- the hazards and risks of handling formaldehyde
 - the health effects of exposure, including signs and symptoms
 - action to take in the event of a spillage of formalin and/or exposure and other emergency procedures
 - the safe handling of formaldehyde
 - circumstances when fumigation is carried out
 - procedure to be followed (detailed in a SOP)
 - precautions to be taken in setting up fumigation
 - containing the gas in the fumigated area
 - use, maintenance and limitations of Respiratory Protective Equipment (RPE) and Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)
 - use of indicator strips
 - use of calibrated equipment to monitor formaldehyde level (formaldemeters) – for nominated users of this equipment
 - factors affecting the efficiency of fumigation
 - venting of fumigant
 - making a fumigated area safe to re-enter – for nominated staff carrying out building/facility fumigations
 - cleaning, transport, storage and disposal procedures
 - accident and incident reporting
- 2.3 RPE must be provided and used where stipulated in the procedure. This should be either full face masks (for which the user must have been face-fit tested within the previous three years) or hoods with belt-packs. Whichever is used, the correct filters must be fitted and replaced at the appropriate interval in accordance with manufacturers' guidance.
- 2.4 All training must be documented in an individual's Training Record and staff must demonstrate competence in fumigation procedures and use of RPE if appropriate.
- 2.5 Competence must be assessed by the Building Officer (person responsible for the facility), their Deputy or other approved manager within the facility.

FUMIGATION PROCEDURE

- 3.1 The purpose of room or building fumigation is to decontaminate:
- when an incident such as a spillage or a power failure has led or potentially led to the release of infectious agent
 - to allow removal of equipment from a laboratory or building
 - animal rooms at the end of experiments
 - to allow access for non health cleared personnel for equipment servicing and building maintenance.

- 3.2 The purpose of MSC and isolator fumigation is to decontaminate:
- in the event of a spillage of infectious agent in the cabinet
 - to remove equipment from the cabinet
 - prior to servicing or maintenance
 - prior to filters being changed
 - or following specific protocols according to local procedures and derogations
- 3.3 Both types of fumigation use a vaporiser or kettle which heats up and releases formaldehyde vapour into the space to be fumigated.
- 3.4 The fumigation area must be sealed from other areas and made as gas tight as possible.
With an MSC this is achieved by correct installation of the closure panel and where necessary sealing with tape and replacing the lid securely on the vaporiser unit. Some MSCs are also fitted with a damper that must be closed during fumigation.
With room or building fumigation this is achieved by sealability testing of the area, closure of gas tight dampers in ducting and sealing door seals with tape.
Spaces adjacent to the fumigation area where it is considered that fumigant could enter must be sealed in the same manner.
Sealability testing must be carried out annually in Containment Level 3 (CL3) facilities and six monthly in Containment level 4 (CL4) facilities. Fumigation must not be carried out if the date of last sealability test exceeds this period or there is evidence that the facility sealability has deteriorated.
- 3.5 Prior to fumigation any absorbent material (other than those intended to be fumigated) must be removed, sealed or contained.
- 3.6 Prior to room fumigation the area (including plant rooms) must be evacuated and secured against unauthorised entry during the fumigation cycle. Cover any unused plug sockets within the room. Signs in accordance with the national Health and Safety must be displayed.
- 3.7 Prior to venting it is essential to ensure that no personnel including contractors are in the vicinity of the exhaust outlet and that exhaust air does not enter nearby windows or ventilation air intakes.

- 3.8 The efficiency of fumigation is affected by:
- The ratio of formalin to water used and therefore the relative humidity created (between 35% and 80% is optimum)
 - The volume of the space to be fumigated (current guidance states this is typically 100ml of formalin in 900ml of water is vaporised for every 28.3m³ of space. However actual volumes used will be dependent on the validation for each facility)
 - The surface area exposed in that space and the presence of absorbent materials such as cardboard boxes
 - Temperature – below 18°C formaldehyde fumigation is less effective and below 9°C formaldehyde sublimates and is less easy to vaporise.
 - Pre-cleaning (e.g. mopping up a spill or removing solid or liquid waste matter) – this will increase efficiency but must only be done without jeopardising safety.

STANDARD OPERATING PROCEDURES (SOP) AND RISK ASSESSMENTS

4.1 MSCs and Isolators

- 4.1.1 The MSC or isolator fumigation procedure must be in place and incorporated into SOP(s) and must include:
- Pre-cleaning procedures prior to fumigation
 - Containment of waste during fumigation (e.g. autoclave tins)
 - Location of equipment and pipettes in MSC during fumigation
 - Materials and chemicals not to be left exposed during fumigation (e.g. absorbent material and incompatible chemicals)
 - Visual indicator strips to be used and their location
 - Volume of formalin and water to be used
 - MSC shutdown procedure including replacement of closure panel
 - RPE and PPE requirements
 - Fumigation cycle time
 - Details of the buddy system used and the pre-fumigation checks (e.g. closure panel secure, vaporiser unit lid secure)
 - Details of the fumigation authorisation process
 - Emergency procedures relating to formalin including spillages and exposure
 - Any post fumigation room formaldehyde level checks required
 - Post fumigation checks on the efficacy of the fumigation
 - Post fumigation venting and cleaning
 - Signage to be applied during and post fumigation
 - Records of fumigation to be kept (forms and logbooks)
 - Disposal of waste post fumigation (e.g. autoclaving)
- The methods for ongoing validation of the fumigation process (see section 5)

4.2 Room or Laboratory

4.2.2 An SOP to describe room or laboratory fumigation procedure must be in place and this must include:

- Pre-cleaning procedures prior to fumigation
- Notification to the Facilities Management Provider
- Containment of waste during fumigation (e.g. in autoclave tins)
- Materials and chemicals not to be left exposed during fumigation (e.g. absorbent material and incompatible chemicals)
- Indicator strips to be used and their location
- Volume of formalin and water to be used
- Location of vaporiser unit(s)
- Fumigation cycle time including venting time
- Details of the buddy system used and minimum number of trained staff required
- Pre-fumigation checks (e.g. area evacuated, no alarms on BMS)
- Details of the fumigation authorisation process
- Emergency procedures relating to formalin including spillages and exposure
- Post fumigation formaldehyde level checks required
- Background levels for each room/area
- Post fumigation checks on the efficiency of the fumigation
- Post fumigation venting and cleaning
- Signage to be applied during and post fumigation
- Details on the records of fumigation to be kept (forms and logbooks)
- Disposal of waste post fumigation (e.g. autoclaving) – if applicable
- The methods for ongoing validation of the fumigation process, for instance, by using biological indicators (see 5.1 to 5.6)
- Emergency fumigation procedures (in the event of release or potential release of the pathogen)

4.2.3 A plan of the facility with volumes of formalin and water used, location of vaporiser unit(s) and location of strips should be appended to the SOP used.

VALIDATION

5.1 To test the effectiveness of fumigation and penetration of the fumigant place spore strips/discs (e.g. carrying *Bacillus subtilis* var. *globigii*, *Bacillus atrophaeus* or *Geobacillus stearothermophilus*) or other representative biological indicator at various points in the room or MSC.

- 5.2 Spore strips must be loaded with a minimum population of 1,000,000 to be used for confirmation of a kill rate of >6-logs.
- 5.3 The positioning of the spores strips/discs should be carefully considered and placed at a point where fumigation concentration is likely to be lowest or where contact time will be the least (e.g. the floor or beneath a piece of equipment).
- 5.4 Comparison on the effect of fumigation between the spore/biological indicator strips used and the agent(s) being handled can be tested in an MSC along with validation of formaldehyde indicator strips.
- 5.5 Formaldehyde indicator strips by Albert Browne Ltd product code 2401 are intended for low temperature steam / formaldehyde sterilisation and a positive result (turning from Oxford Blue to Emerald Green) demonstrates 6-logs reduction with a 25% safety margin.
If these are used during fumigation then ongoing validation of the fumigation cycle must be carried out every five years.
- If using an alternative formaldehyde indicator strip that does not indicate a 6 log reduction then ongoing validation of the fumigation cycle must be carried out each year.
- Ongoing validation tests should only be carried out during planned fumigations.
- 5.6 All validation and ongoing validation must be documented and recorded.

RECORD KEEPING

- 6.1 Records of all fumigations must be kept.
- 6.2 Post fumigation formaldehyde level checks must be recorded.
- 6.3 Management approval for each fumigation must be recorded.
- 6.4 Records of RPE servicing and maintenance including filter changes must be kept.

MONITORING

7.1 Monitoring

To ensure the effectiveness of and compliance with this Best Practice the following arrangements are in place.

7.1.1 **Proactive Monitoring**

Monitoring takes place proactively in the following ways:

- Formal audit by the Institutes Health and Safety Department and line management which includes topics related to all aspects of fumigation and check adherence to safe systems (this SOPs and Risk Assessments) of work.

7.1.2 **Reactive Monitoring**

Monitoring takes place reactively by:

- Identification by employee reporting.
- Accident/incident reporting.

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Document History

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